

PARA SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF THROMBOSED EXTERNAL HEMORRHOIDS USING JALAUKA VACHARANA: A CASE REPORT

Dr. Vaibhav Jain*¹, Dr. Rajendra Kumar Dixit², Dr. Jitendra Patel³, Dr Akhila Sundar⁴

¹MS Scholar, Second Year, Dept. of Shalya Tantra Rani Dullaiya Smriti Ayurved P. G. College and Hospital Bhopal (M.P.)

²Associate Professor, Dept. of Shalya Tantra Rani Dullaiya Smriti Ayurved P. G. College and Hospital Bhopal (M.P.)

³MD Scholar, Second Year, Dept. of Samhita Siddhant, Govt. (Auto.) Ayurved College Nipaniya Rewa (M.P.)

⁴Assistant Professor, Dept. of Shalya Tantra Rani Dullaiya Smriti Ayurved P. G. College and Hospital Bhopal (M.P.).

Article Received on 16 Feb. 2026,
Article Revised on 05 March 2026,
Article Published on 16 March 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19046933>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Vaibhav Jain

MS Scholar, Second Year, Dept. of Shalya Tantra Rani Dullaiya Smriti Ayurved P. G. College and Hospital Bhopal (M.P.).

How to cite this Article: Dr. Vaibhav Jain*¹, Dr. Rajendra Kumar Dixit², Dr. Jitendra Patel³, Dr Akhila Sundar⁴. (2026). Para Surgical Management of Thrombosed External Hemorrhoids Using Jalaukavacharana: A Case Report. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(6), 1210-1216.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

The external hemorrhoidal venous system's tortuosity and distension cause the thrombosed external pile, which is situated distal to the dentate line. The abrupt swelling and engorgement of a hemorrhoidal vessel may permit blood to collect and then clot, resulting in the Acute Thrombosed External Pile mass, a bluish-purple enlargement accompanied by excruciating pain and soreness. The effect of using Leech is assessed in the current situation of TEP (thrombosed external pile). The major goal is to evaluate how well Leech works for the patient's bothersome signs and symptoms, which include pain, edema, soreness, and discoloration. Leech therapy is used to successfully manage the situation. The substances hirudin, calin, and factor Xa found in leech saliva aid in suppressing the formation of a blood clot in an external pile mass and relieve the patient's symptoms.

KEYWORDS: Leech Therapy, Thrombosed External Pile, Jaloka avcharana, Arsha Chikitsa.

INTRODUCTION

Arsha was one of the Ashta Mahagada (eight major diseases), which are thought to be challenging to treat because of their chronicity, according to Acharya Sushruta, who is revered as the Father of Surgery.^[1] Ayurvedic scriptures state that Mansakila, which refers to the flesh or muscular tissue, can be used to describe ailments affecting the soft tissues around the Guda (anal canal), whereas Arsha (hemorrhoid) can be defined as such. When it becomes a pathological condition, it can impede the Gudmarga, or the anal passage, giving the patient great anguish and torturing them like an enemy.^[2]

The radicles of the superior, middle, and inferior rectal veins generate hemorrhoids, which are dilated veins inside the anal canal in the subepithelial region.^[3]

The development of a blood clot in one or more veins beneath the anal skin is the hallmark of a thrombosed external hemorrhoid, which causes excruciating swelling and inflammation.^[4]

The clot usually gives the enlarged area a bluish appearance. The focus of Acharya Sushruta is on Visravana or One possible cure for this excruciating illness is raktamokshana, or bloodletting.^[5]

In particular, bloodletting is advised to alleviate venous stagnation, irritation, and congestion. Raktamokshana, whether via Jalauka (leech therapy) or other means, is recommended by Acharya Sushruta.^[6]

When secondary complications like thrombosis are present, surgical intervention may be contraindicated.^[7] Because it can complicate surgery and increase the risk of post-operative complications. Instead, conservative or non-invasive treatment such as Raktamokshana (bloodletting) with leech therapy (Jalaukavacharan) can preferred. The effect of leech therapy (Jalaukawacharana) in thrombosed external piles has been studied in this case and Efficacy was evaluated.

CASE STUDY

Presenting Complaint

A 23-year-old woman arrived at our outpatient department complaining of pain and a mass in her perium during the previous two weeks.

History of Presenting Complaint

Two weeks ago, the patient appeared normal before experiencing a severe swelling over her anal area. The ache got worse over time. She finds it difficult to pass stools comfortably because the pain is worst when she sits, lies on her back, and has bowel movements. She came to our hospital for additional assessment and care because of ongoing, excruciating pain and agony.

Past History

No H/O - HTN, DM, Asthma, TB or any other major illness.

Personal History

Appetite - Good Sleep - Disturbed Bowel – Constipated.

Micturition

Normal.

Habits

Non smoker, Non alcoholic.

Examinations

BP - 100/ 70 mmhg

Pulse - 68/min

Temp - 97.4 F

Spo2 – 98%

Systemic

CVS – S1 S2 normal

CNS - conscious, oriented RS - AEBE clear

P/A - soft and normal

Local Examination

Ano rectal examination

Inspection : reddish black globular mass at 5 o'clock

Palpation : mass is tender

Proctoscopy : not done due to severe pain

Blood Investigations

Hb - 12 gm/dl

TLC - 7000/cumm

Rbc - 5.42 millions/cumm

MCV - 74.8 fl MCHC - 34.6 gm/dl

MCH - 28.9 picogram

Platelet count - 2 Lakh/cumm

Bleeding time - 02 min 04 sec

Clotting time - 05 min 22 sec

HbsAg - Non-Reactive HIV 1 - Non-Reactive HIV 2 - Non-Reactive

METHODOLOGY

After thorough investigations and evaluations, leech therapy (Jalaukavacharana) was planned. Written consent was taken.

Leech Application**Purva Karma**

To reduce the chance of infection, the afflicted perianal area was thoroughly cleaned and dried. Leeches that are not toxic (*Hirudo medicinalis*) were chosen to receive treatment. To aid in their cleansing and to increase their hunger, the leeches were submerged in turmeric water.^[8]

Pradhan Karma

A little puncture was created in the thrombosed external hemorrhoid's inflamed region. *Hirudo medicinalis* leeches were applied to particular locations at 5 o'clock around the hemorrhoid. The leeches started sucking blood as soon as they were put on the punctured sites. A moist bandage was placed over the leeches' bodies as they started to draw blood. The procedure was carried out until the leech detached on its own.^[9]

Pashchat Karma

The bite site was wrapped with gauze soaked with Yashtimadhu and dusted with turmeric powder once the leeches had spontaneously disengaged. Ghrita used a loose bandage to secure. The leeches were given turmeric to put in their mouths to make them throw up. The leeches were gently pressed from the tail to the mouth to release any blood they may have consumed once they started to evacuate their stomach contents. After that, they were cleaned

with fresh water and put away in different, clearly marked bottles with fresh water.^[10]

It was recommended that the patient take sitz baths twice a day total number of sittings completed over a series of days.

Pathya Apathya

Pathya - Laghu, Snigdha, Raktavardhak, Amlarahit aahara sevan.

Apathya - Vyayama, Maithuna, Raag, Diwaswapa, Kshar, Amla, Lavana, Katu, sheeta aaharasevan.^[11]

OBSERVATIONS

Variables	BT	Day 1	Day 4	Day 7
Pain	+++	++	++	-
edema	+++	++	++	-
Discoloration	+++	++	++	-

BT: Before treatment, Mild : +, Moderate: ++, Severe: +++

No symptom: - Symptoms were evaluated using a grading system based on their severity. After the First session of Jalaukavacharana, there was a 30% decrease in the bluish discoloration of the thrombosed haemorrhoids, approx. 60% reduction in pain and a moderate decrease in swelling was observed.

On the 7th day, bluish discolouration, pain and edema resolved completely.

RESULT

The patient experienced a reduction in pain over the thrombosed haemorrhoids as soon as the leech treatment started. she experienced less discomfort. There was noticeable decrease in discolouration following the second sitting.

The patient experienced 80% reduction in all symptoms following the 2nd sessions of Jalaukavacharan.

The patient is completely satisfied with the treatment and was relieved of all symptoms on 7th day.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

India has been using Raktamokshana, an Ayurvedic therapeutic technique, for thousands of years. It is regarded as one of the Panchakarma practices that are five techniques for bio-

purification. Among the several methods used in Ayurveda for bloodletting, the use of leeches (Jalaukavacharana) is one of the most prominent. These leeches' saliva contains hirudin, a strong anticoagulant that prevents blood coagulation and makes it easier to extract blood from the injured area.^[12]

By increasing circulation and aiding in the removal of stagnant blood, hyaluronidase improves the effectiveness of anticoagulants and aids in the breakup of clots.

This ancient method supports tissue healing and general health while successfully addressing pain, edema, and local immunity by utilizing the therapeutic qualities of hirudin, hyaluronidase, Eglin, and other bioactive substances. They improve capillary exchange by increasing blood circulation in the surrounding tissues as well as in the afflicted organs.

This aids in the dissolution of structured blood clots and the reduction of discomfort and edema. Additionally, leeches increase local immunity.

Applying leech has a thrombolytic effect on thrombosed hemorrhoids.^[13]

Based on the above observations and therapeutic effects discussed, we can draw conclusion regarding the efficacy of Raktamokshana using Jalauka (*Hirudo medicinalis*) for managing thrombosed external hemorrhoids. Leech therapy effectively provides comprehensive relief from the symptoms associated with thrombosed external hemorrhoids, including significant pain reduction, swelling, and discomfort. It has various pharmacological properties like antimicrobial, mucolytic and thrombolytic. In addition to this benefit, the method is cost effective, less time consuming and an OPD procedure.

REFERENCES

1. Sushruta samhita, Ayurvedatva Sandipika, Dr. Ambikadatta Shastri, Sutra Sthan- 33/4,5 Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi Edition: Reprint, 2016; 163.
2. Ashtanga Hridaya of Vagbhata with commentaries of Sarvangasundara of Arundatta and Ayurvedarasayana of Hemadri, Dr. Anna Moreshwar Kunte & Krsna Ramchandra Sastri Navre, Nidanasthana, Chapter No. 7, Verse 1, Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi, Edition, 2017; 490.
3. S. Das, A concise text book of surgery, publisher S. Das, old Mayors' court, kolkata; 9th edition, 2016; 1074.
4. S. Das, A concise text book of surgery, publisher S. Das, old Mayors' court, kolkata; 9th

- edition, 2016; 1075.
5. Sushruta samhita, Ayurvedatva Sandipika, Dr.Ambikadatta Shastri, Chikitsa Sthan- 6/7 Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi Edition: Reprint, 2016; 47.
 6. Sushruta samhita, AyurvedatvaSandipika, Dr.Ambikadatta Shastri, Sutra Sthan- 13/3 Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi Edition: Reprint, 2016; 57.
 7. Sriram Bhat M, SRB's manual of surgery., Jaypee publications, 5th edition, 972. 8. Sushruta samhita, Ayurvedatva Sandipika, Dr. Ambikadatta Shastri, Sutra Sthan- 13/19 Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi Edition: Reprint, 2016; 60.
 8. Sushruta samhita, Ayurvedatva Sandipika, Dr. Ambikadatta Shastri, Sutra Sthan- 13/20 Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi Edition: Reprint, 2016; 60.
 9. Sushruta samhita, Ayurvedatva Sandipika, Dr.Ambikadatta Shastri, Sutra Sthan- 13/21-23 Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi Edition: Reprint, 2016; 60.
 10. Sushruta samhita, Ayurvedatva Sandipika, Dr. Ambikadatta Shastri, Sutra Sthan- 14/38 Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan Varanasi Edition: Reprint, 2016; 72.
 11. Pradnya J. Bhagat, Subhash Y. Raut¹, Arun M. Lakhapati, Clinical efficacy of Jalaukawacharana (leech application) in Thrombosed piles, AYU journal, Apr-Jun., 2012; 33(2): 261-263 (www.ayujournal.org)
 12. Srivastava A, Sharma R. A brief review on applications of leech therapy. Arch Appl Sci Res, 2010; 2: 271-4. Available from: (<http://www.scholarsresearchlibrary.com/archive.html>)